

Supplemental Table 2: Summary of milk production and FE phenotypes in the 39 Assaf ewes analyzed in this work. For each animal (Sample_ID), the type of lambing (single or twins), the means ($\pm$ coefficient of variation in %) of the milk production traits: milk yield (MY), milk protein percentage (PP), milk fat percentage (FP) and milk lactose percentage (LC) are presented. The FE parameters recorded during the three-week evaluation period: Dry matter intake (DMI), feed efficiency indices RFI and FCR and the high, medium or low-efficiency group for each FE-index are also presented.

Sample_ID	Lambing type	MY	FP	PP	LC	DMI	RFI	FCR	RFI-group	FCR-group
ewe_1	Single	2.6326 ($\pm$ 7.009)	66.1583 ($\pm$ 11.5764)	49.1166 ($\pm$ 3.6781)	52.5875 ($\pm$ 0.9924)	2.6097 ($\pm$ 13.5202)	-0.2509	1.0878	L-RFI	L-FCR
ewe_2	Single	2.5483 ($\pm$ 10.05)	59.7708 ($\pm$ 11.4358)	46.0708 ($\pm$ 1.5905)	49.7625 ($\pm$ 1.5833)	2.7143 ($\pm$ 12.8937)	-0.2029	1.2489	L-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_3	Single	1.534 ($\pm$ 10.9235)	55.2791 ($\pm$ 7.2772)	49.8333 ($\pm$ 2.8279)	48.4833 ($\pm$ 0.9969)	2.4618 ($\pm$ 14.7778)	0.0378	1.9170	M-RFI	H-FCR
ewe_5	Twins	2.6295 ($\pm$ 13.8675)	55.3533 ($\pm$ 17.57)	49.6208 ($\pm$ 6.0499)	48.375 ($\pm$ 8.6072)	2.985 ($\pm$ 10.676)	0.1468	1.3566	H-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_6	Single	3.0433 ($\pm$ 12.4875)	52.8125 ($\pm$ 10.1955)	49.6291 ($\pm$ 3.467)	49.3708 ($\pm$ 1.712)	3.1564 ($\pm$ 12.6419)	0.0215	1.2667	M-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_7	Twins	2.5264 ($\pm$ 14.7264)	56.6875 ($\pm$ 13.0071)	46.0875 ($\pm$ 2.5623)	52.1041 ($\pm$ 1.5631)	2.9851 ($\pm$ 8.9805)	0.1386	1.4218	H-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_9	Single	2.2681 ($\pm$ 4.6351)	45.325 ($\pm$ 11.8893)	43.0395 ($\pm$ 1.4423)	52.3625 ($\pm$ 1.1059)	2.7914 ($\pm$ 7.0479)	-0.0042	1.6693	M-RFI	H-FCR
ewe_11	Single	1.8273 ($\pm$ 9.4455)	58.7333 ($\pm$ 8.479)	53.3375 ($\pm$ 3.3903)	51.7416 ($\pm$ 0.4655)	2.513 ($\pm$ 13.5504)	-0.0077	1.5686	M-RFI	H-FCR
ewe_12	Single	2.5688 ($\pm$ 5.2107)	56.8333 ($\pm$ 7.2795)	46.6583 ($\pm$ 2.3396)	52.4916 ($\pm$ 1.5613)	2.9567 ($\pm$ 6.4086)	-0.0045	1.3792	M-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_13	Twins	2.0779 ($\pm$ 8.9937)	54.7833 ($\pm$ 8.935)	53.275 ($\pm$ 3.6168)	51.725 ($\pm$ 1.1016)	2.2864 ($\pm$ 11.8492)	-0.1022	1.2969	L-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_14	Twins	2.1805 ($\pm$ 13.4194)	53.0916 ($\pm$ 13.5388)	47.5208 ($\pm$ 3.9736)	52.0666 ($\pm$ 1.3271)	2.7157 ($\pm$ 11.352)	0.0120	1.5344	M-RFI	H-FCR
ewe_21	Twins	2.0074 ($\pm$ 13.6678)	56.5833 ($\pm$ 9.7363)	52.9791 ($\pm$ 1.0708)	52.3458 ($\pm$ 1.9902)	2.456 ($\pm$ 11.3867)	-0.1417	1.4227	L-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_23	Single	2.3153 ($\pm$ 9.0312)	56.4916 ($\pm$ 6.5241)	51.425 ($\pm$ 1.8887)	50.475 ($\pm$ 2.4506)	3.0144 ($\pm$ 5.9401)	0.0645	1.5269	M-RFI	H-FCR

ewe_27	Single	3.994 (±4.7351)	50.0833 (±14.6108)	45.6125 (±1.6105)	51.9625 (±1.1477)	3.0774 (±5.5542)	-0.0388	0.9851	M-RFI	L-FCR
ewe_28	Single	2.0953 (±10.3145)	71.5875 (±14.7041)	50.05 (±1.8374)	50.325 (±2.5352)	2.2628 (±10.756)	-0.3434	1.1321	M-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_29	Single	3.0422 (±6.2195)	60.9708 (±11.8213)	49.1666 (±3.499)	51.3833 (±1.2669)	3.1818 (±10.4901)	0.0276	1.1957	M-RFI	L-FCR
ewe_30	Single	2.3596 (±3.1383)	58.7958 (±13.6915)	50.5041 (±2.5229)	51.7083 (±0.9553)	3.1092 (±7.5722)	-0.0948	1.5233	M-RFI	L-FCR
ewe_31	Twins	3.6446 (±5.5064)	56.1666 (±12.2883)	52.0875 (±1.111)	52.65 (±1.4708)	3.4916 (±7.0422)	0.1664	1.1229	H-RFI	L-FCR
ewe_37	Twins	2.2271 (±11.3744)	74.4666 (±13.2773)	51.1875 (±3.1379)	50.5333 (±2.2477)	2.7006 (±13.3996)	-0.0736	1.2383	L-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_4	Twins	2.1795 (±13.566)	71.6833 (±10.3585)	50.5708 (±7.4417)	47.7125 (±10.0674)	2.3072 (±14.8358)	0.0752	1.1064	M-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_8	Single	2.3133 (±7.3367)	50.8904 (±9.1839)	45.3125 (±2.2281)	50.7083 (±4.0417)	2.8494 (±11.3953)	0.2169	1.5660	H-RFI	H-FCR
ewe_10	Twins	1.752 (±6.2247)	57.6208 (±11.4378)	48.5395 (±2.237)	48.5687 (±2.2935)	2.4365 (±9.6415)	0.0502	1.6396	M-RFI	H-FCR
ewe_15	Single	2.1468 (±8.9784)	57.2541 (±8.1746)	51.8541 (±3.2421)	51.3625 (±0.6493)	2.6905 (±6.0377)	0.0182	1.4575	M-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_16	Single	3.0274 (±9.9217)	51.5952 (±14.8834)	47.1041 (±2.8673)	53.5416 (±1.0995)	2.9899 (±11.815)	0.0671	1.2356	M-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_17	Single	2.4667 (±9.6401)	56.0333 (±8.8609)	46.3916 (±1.4312)	52.1875 (±1.0561)	2.918 (±14.0959)	0.1378	1.4292	H-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_18	Single	1.5776 (±11.4622)	52.8125 (±9.9637)	44.8958 (±0.9692)	51.2083 (±1.8443)	2.3607 (±13.2246)	0.0024	1.8741	M-RFI	H-FCR
ewe_19	Single	2.0006 (±11.3778)	53.9875 (±10.6816)	46.0083 (±3.2172)	54.125 (±1.6116)	2.5348 (±12.7481)	-0.1365	1.5612	L-RFI	H-FCR
ewe_20	Single	3.0956 (±11.233)	52.5375 (±16.7097)	44.3208 (±4.0521)	53.0541 (±2.1093)	3.273 (±13.9046)	0.1944	1.3316	H-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_22	Single	3.2713 (±5.5187)	58.15 (±7.508)	51.1166 (±2.2739)	51.9666 (±2.0586)	3.3273 (±9.291)	0.1226	1.1785	H-RFI	L-FCR
ewe_24	Single	2.2454 (±8.9731)	47.7375 (±11.9957)	50.0791 (±5.3298)	51.9416 (±3.1925)	2.9606 (±11.6025)	0.1129	1.6803	H-RFI	H-FCR
ewe_25	Single	2.6569 (±5.3213)	57.8333 (±15.5667)	46.0083 (±1.2127)	48.0666 (±1.5382)	2.621 (±13.2019)	0.0507	1.1760	M-RFI	L-FCR

ewe_26	Single	3.1574 (±10.8202)	56.9904 (±19.6117)	43.5458 (±5.6661)	50.6208 (±1.2855)	2.8735 (±14.6401)	-0.0228	1.1068	M-RFI	L-FCR
ewe_32	Twins	2.9228 (±5.2495)	57.2625 (±9.1642)	53.2375 (±2.8728)	50.7375 (±1.4842)	3.0434 (±9.3853)	-0.1281	1.2025	L-RFI	L-FCR
ewe_33	Single	1.9434 (±13.5906)	60.9904 (±11.1823)	52.3666 (±4.6215)	47.7708 (±3.9959)	2.6206 (±12.0844)	0.0731	1.5175	H-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_34	Twins	2.9525 (±8.1361)	49.6208 (±10.5409)	44.1375 (±3.4893)	54.5 (±1.6826)	2.8109 (±11.0868)	-0.0861	1.2324	L-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_35	Twins	3.0649 (±7.9085)	63.725 (±10.5546)	49.1416 (±3.9075)	51.9083 (±2.5676)	2.8081 (±10.9427)	-0.1776	1.0247	L-RFI	L-FCR
ewe_36	Twins	2.7011 (±9.5337)	54.5583 (±8.3835)	50.1291 (±2.1969)	49.4875 (±0.8366)	2.9731 (±5.3079)	0.2768	1.3208	H-RFI	M-FCR
ewe_38	Twins	2.9723 (±10.148)	62.9416 (±10.9382)	49.3041 (±2.0431)	50.1125 (±0.878)	2.9123 (±12.2015)	-0.1584	1.1018	L-RFI	L-FCR
ewe_39	Twins	2.2775 (±8.6327)	66.1916 (±12.8744)	50.325 (±3.3564)	52.7541 (±0.8436)	2.7117 (±10.3038)	-0.0393	1.2988	M-RFI	M-FCR